

(IIJIF) Impact Factor- 4.172

Regd. No. : 1687-2006-2007

ISSN 0974 - 7648

J I G Y A S A

**AN INTERDISCIPLINARY PEER REVIEWED
REFEREED RESEARCH JOURNAL**

Chief Editor : *Indukant Dixit*

Executive Editor : *Shashi Bhushan Poddar*

Editor
Reeta Yadav

Volume 13

March 2020

No. III

Published by
PODDAR FOUNDATION
Taranagar Colony
Chhittupur, BHU, Varanasi
www.jigyasabhu.blogspot.com
www.jigyasabhu.com
E-mail : jigyasabhu@gmail.com
Mob. 9415390515, 0542 2366370

- **Determine and Analyze Consumer Buying behaviour for Hand Sanitizer** 389-401
Silky Verma, Master of Business Administration (MBA) (2019-2021) , Lovely Professional University, Phagwara, Punjab
- **Building Retail Brands through Visual Merchandising : An Integral Review** 402-409
Soumya Chowdhury, Research Scholar, Faculty of Commerce, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi
- **A Study of the Communication Discourse on the Vaishnva Consciousness of Chhayavadi Hindi Poets (Special Reference: Sumitranandan Pant's Poetic Approach)** 410-420
Ishan Tripathi, Research Scholar (Doctoral Fellow (I.C.S.S.R.)), Department of Journalism & Mass Communication, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi
- **Prospects of Agro- Based Industries for Rural Development in Vaishali District** 421-425
Devendra Prasad Sah, Research Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Geography, L.N.Mithila Univ. Darbhanga
- **Level of Literacy and Socio- Economic Condition of S.C. Population of Begusarai District** 426-430
Indradeo Ram, Research Scholar, P.G. Dept. of Geography, L.N.Mithila Univ. Darbhanga
- **Judicial Review of Government Contracting: Plethora of Paradox under Umbrella of Equitable Principle of Unfairness** 431-439
Dr. Meena Wagde, Assistant Professor (Law), BKSJN Govt. P.G. College, Shajapur (M.P.)
- **Online Purchasing: A Study on the Consumers in the City of Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh** 440-449
Harsh Agrawal, Research Scholar, Department of Journalism & Mass Communication, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

Online Purchasing: A Study on the Consumers in the City of Varanasi, Uttar Pradesh

*Harsh Agrawal **

Electronic commerce, commonly known as e-commerce, refers to the buying and selling of products or services over electronic systems such as the internet and other computer networks. Internet is the rapidest growing media during the past decade. Especially, online shopping is a rapidly growing e-commerce area. Online stores are usually available 24 hours a day, and many consumers have internet access both at work and at home. A successful web store is not just a good looking website with dynamic technical features, listed in many search engines. This study aims to establish a preliminary assessment, evaluation and understanding of the characteristics of online shopping. An effort has been made to investigate online consumer behaviour, which in turn provides E-marketers with a constructional framework for fine-tuning their E-businesses' strategies.

Introduction : Generally speaking the trend of e-commerce has increased rapidly in recent years with the development of Internet and due to the easy accessibility of Internet usage. Easy access to Internet has driven consumers to shop online. Globally more than 627 million people have done online shopping so far. Books, airline tickets/reservations, clothing/shoes videos/games and other electronic products are the most popular items purchased on the Internet. (AC Nielsen Report on Global Consumer Attitudes towards Online Shopping, 2007).

The process of online buying behavior consists of five steps and it is similar to traditional shopping behavior (Liang and Lai 2000). For instance, consumer recognize the need for buying some product (book), they refers to the Internet to buy online and start to search for the information and look for all the alternatives and finally make a purchase which best fits to their needs. Before making final purchase consumers are bombarded by several factors which limits or influence consumers for the final decision.

* Research Scholar, Department of Journalism & Mass Communication, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi

The main theme of the study is to know the factors that influence the consumer's behaviors towards online shopping. Researchers will also focus on to find out which types of products are usually purchased by online shoppers. According to the online survey within few American students, Case, Burns, and Dick, (2001, p.873) concluded that "Internet knowledge, income, and education level are especially powerful predictors of Internet purchases among university Students".

The problem area that is Consumers attitude towards online shopping will determine the attractive factors that influence consumers to shop online and those factors will help marketers to formulate their strategies towards online marketing respectively. As our area of research will be on Uttar Pradesh and specifically on Varanasi so our research thesis will not only be helpful for the marketers in general but specifically will be helpful for the marketers in Uttar Pradesh.

Statement of the Problem

An increasing number and variety of firms and organizations are exploiting and creating business opportunities on the Internet. In order to gain competitive edge in the market, marketers need to know the consumer behavior in the field of online shopping. So it is important to analyze and identify the factors which influence consumers to shop online in order to capture the demands of consumers.

Aim: Analyze the online purchasing behavior of online shoppers living in Varanasi, U.P.

Objectives: The objectives of the study are to:

- Discover factors that motivate people to shop online;
- Find out the type of goods purchased usually by online shoppers;
- Identify the socio-economic profile of online shoppers; and
- Find out the process adopted by online shoppers for online purchase.

Method : The research '**Online Purchasing: A study of the Online Consumers in the city of Varanasi**' is a type of market research. Researcher needed some data about the online consumers' behavior to analyze their online purchasing behavior. To get this data, the researchers interacted with the online shoppers and asked questions. So, Survey method was used to gather information

Variables

Objective	Independent Variable	Dependent Variable
Discover Factors that motivate people to shop online.	Availability of large variety Time saving Payment method Home delivery facility Return policy Discount offer	Factors motivating online shopping behavior of consumers
Identify socio-economic profile of online shoppers	Age Occupation Gender Income Marital Status	Socio-economic status of online shoppers
Find out process adopted by online shoppers.	Channel of purchasing Comparison of products Payment Method adopted	Process adopted by online shoppers.

Sampling design : It is not possible for the researcher to have a list of the online shoppers in Varanasi in such a short period of time. So he/she opted non probability sampling. Since the researcher needs samples who shop online; Snowball Sampling design met this criterion. Thus snowball sampling design has been used in this study. In this type of sampling, some respondents; who fulfill the criterion are contacted, and then these respondents suggest some other respondents who fulfill the criterion. This chain continues till the desired number of respondents was contacted.

Sample size : Keeping in view the limitation of time and resources researcher has decided to take the sample of 100 respondents for the research. He contacted 100 samples, but 32 samples refused to give response. Thus, response of 68 samples has been recorded on questionnaire.

Tools: Questionnaire

The questionnaire is carefully designed to meet the requirements of the research. The questionnaire is divided in four sections; each section fulfilling purpose of an objective of this study.

Section A consists of one question that determines the factors that motivate online consumers to shop online. Section B contains one question that finds out which type of goods are usually purchased online by online shoppers. Section C has five objective questions that identify the socio-economic profile of online shoppers. Section D

consists of three questions that find out the process done by online shoppers while purchasing online.

Data Collection Method : The researcher contacted persons in his/her acquaintance who do online shopping. These persons were contacted and asked to fill up questionnaire and suggest some other persons who usually shop online. Now these persons suggested some other persons who shop online. Thus the chain continued till the appropriate number of samples was contacted.

Findings : Findings of this study has been divided into four parts,

- The first part shows the gathered data on factors that motivate people to shop online;
- The second part presents the data on type of goods purchased usually by online shoppers;
- The third part carries the socio-economic profile of online shoppers and
- The fourth part consists of gathered data on process adopted by online shoppers for online purchase.

1. Gathered data on factors that motivate people to shop online

There are many factors that motivate people to shop online. To consider all the factors in a particular study is quite impossible. So the researcher chose seven factors to be calculated in this study.

Figure 1: Factors Motivating people to shop online

The study showed that 54% of the online shoppers, considered in this study, think ‘availability of large variety’ and ‘home delivery facility’ is the main driving force while 51% of the online shoppers shop online because of ‘Discount offer’. Other motivating forces, which had led to online shopping, were ‘time saving’ (50%) and Price comparison facility (38%).

2. Type of goods purchased usually by online shoppers

It is depicted in the Figure 4.2 that the highest category of goods purchased by the respondents is ‘Mobile & Accessories’ (56%), clothing (54%), books (48%), footwear (47%) and watches (38%). Besides this, respondents also purchase ‘Camera &

Accessories (28%)', 'Home Theatre/ Speaker/ MP3/I Pod (25%)' and 'Bed sheet/ Curtain/ Cushion & Pillow Cover (22%)'. Whereas the lowest category of goods purchased online are Air conditioner, Refrigerator, TV, Desktop PCs Furniture and Washing Machine.

Figure 4.2: Goods purchased online

3. Socio-economic profile of online shoppers

This section was used in order to establish the socio-economic profile of consumer. It is used to find consumers' age, gender, profession, income and marital status.

3.1 Age of Online shoppers : Age was included to find out if there is a significant relationship to what impact the factors have on different age groups. Age is a demographic value that can be used in order to further explain and elaborate on some of the other questions of this study.

Figure 3.1 Age of Online Shoppers

The research was conducted among the people who shop online in the Varanasi city. The age groups, 18-25 years and 26-35 years held the majority of respondents, 66% and 24% respectively. This data explained that the consumers we investigated had a majority number of younger online shoppers.

3.2 Occupation of Online Shoppers : Occupation was included to find out if there is a significant relationship to what impact the factors have on consumers having different occupation. It also help in finding which type of goods are purchased by them.

It is clear from the figure 4.3.2 that majority of respondents of this study are students i.e. 61%, While 21% of the respondents are self employed.

Figure 3.2 Occupation of Online Shoppers

3.3 Gender of Online shoppers : Gender was included in the survey in order to find out if there is a difference between men and women

concerning the beliefs toward the factors, goods purchased and process adopted for online shopping. The following figure shows the distribution of the male and female respondents that were included in the survey.

Figure 3.3 Gender of Online Shoppers

The distribution of male and female respondents shows a majority of male respondents (68%), compared to female respondents (32%). Males respondents (68%) are approximately twice of female respondents (32%). An explanation for this distribution might be that male respondents have been more willing to answer the questionnaire.

3.4 Monthly income of online shoppers : Income was used in the questionnaire mainly to find if the respondents that have higher income spend more money online or not.

Income plays a huge role in purchasing behavior. Figure states that 44% of the respondents have income less than Rs.15000. The distribution of the variable income is highly connected with the fact that the majority of respondent is student and, therefore, has a lower income. It is also found that 24% of the respondents didn't specify their income.

Figure 3.4 Monthly income of Online Shoppers

3.5 Marital Status of online shoppers : Marital status was included in the survey in order to find out if there is a difference between married person and single person concerning the beliefs toward the factors, goods purchased and process adopted for online shopping.

The following figure shows the distribution of the male and female respondents that were included in the survey.

Figure 3.5 Marital Status of Online Shoppers

Marital status affects the need of product for individual. Single person's need differs from that of Married person. Figure states that 71% of the respondents were 'single'. While 19% were married.

4. Process adopted by online shoppers

4.1 Medium used by online shoppers : According to the Figure 4.1; 46% of the respondents use Mobile App for online shopping and 38% use websites for online shopping.

Figure 4.1 Medium used for Online shopping

4.2 Before-purchasing process : From the figure 4.2 it is clear that almost all the online shoppers compare products over different online shops. 88% of the respondents agreed that they compare products before purchasing.

Figure 4.2 Comparison of products

4.3 Payment method adopted by online shoppers : It is clearly depicted from the figure 4.4.3; that Cash on delivery (57%) is the most popular payment method among online shoppers. 'Debit card' and 'online banking' options are also used by the respondents to shop online.

Figure 4.3 Payment Method for online shopping

Conclusion : The e-commerce is one of the biggest things that have taken the business by a storm. It is creating an entire new economy, which has a huge potential and is fundamentally changing the way businesses are done. It is believed that electronic commerce will become a huge industry in the coming years and online shopping is now becoming a significant part of the consumer's daily life to meet their never ending requirements in a convenient way. A huge buyers and sellers across demographics are shopping online because of the changing lifestyles and shopping habits. It is seen that despite the immense possibilities available on the internet it is mainly used for mailing, chatting and surfing. E-mail applications still constitute the bulk of net traffic in the country.

In this study we examined some factors affecting on online shopping behavior of consumers, type of goods purchased by them online. This study also revealed their socio economic status and the process adopted by them while shopping online.

The socio economic profile of respondents has a huge impact on their online shopping behavior. Findings suggest that people who shop online are generally between 18 to 25 years old and are students. Males and singles tend to shop online more than females. People who earn Rs. 15000 & less monthly prefer to buy online.

Online shoppers mostly purchase Mobile & accessories, clothing books, footwear and watches. While big electronic products like Refrigerator, Washing Machine, AC, Desktop and TV are less

purchased online. In contrast people purchase MP3, iPod and Home theater systems online.

Availability of large variety, Home delivery Facility, Discount Offer and Time savings are the factors that motivates them to purchase online. They shop online through Mobile App and websites both as not much difference is found between them. But before purchasing they do compare products over different online shops. Cash on Delivery (COD) payment is the most reliable mode of payment among online shoppers.

References :

- Sharma R., Mehta D. and Sharma S. (2014). Understanding Online Shopping Behaviour of Indian Shoppers. *International Journal of Management and Business Studies*, 4(3), 9-18.
- Pawar S.S., More D.K. and Bhola D. Influence Undergraduate Students For Online Buying.
- *International Journal of Logistics and Supply Chain Management Perspectives* © Pezzottaite Journals., 1200-1208.
- Balaji P. (2015). Online shopping behaviour of college students. *International Journal of Commerce and Business Management*, 8(1), 84-87.
- Ranganathan C. and Ganapathy S. (2002). Key dimensions of business-to-consumer web sites. *Management*, 39(6), 457-465.
- R.Gopal, and Jindoliya Deepika. Consumer buying behaviour towards online shopping: a literature review *International Journal of Information Research and Review* © Gopal and Deepika Jindoliya., 2016
- Andrew, J. R and Vanitha, S. (2004). A typology of online shoppers based on shopping motivations, *Journal of Business Research* Vol. 57 PP. 748–757
- Amit, B. Sanjoy, Ghose. (2004). A latent class segmentation analysis of e-shoppers, *Journal of Business Research*. Vol.57, PP.758-767.
- Andrew, J. R & Vanitha, S. (2004). A typology of online shoppers based on shopping motivations. *Journal of Business Research*. Vol. 57 (2004) PP.748– 757
- Bell, E & Bryman, A. 2007, *Business research methods*, New York: Oxford university press.
- Boudraeu, M.C and Watson R.T (2006). “Internet Advertising Strategy Alignment” *Internet Research*. Vol.16 (1), PP.23-37
- Davis, F. D., Bagozzi, R. P. and Warshaw, P. R. (1989). User Acceptance of Computer Technology, *Journal of Management Science*, Vol35 (8), PP.982-1003
